

A NEW CALCULATION METHOD OF TRANSFORMATION TOUGHENING IN CERAMICS*

Biao Wang, Shanyi Du and Shiung Chen**

School of Astronautics,
Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin 150006, P. R. China

Abstract

A new calculation method of transformation toughening is proposed in this paper. The crack tip is assumed to be surrounded by a zone which contains a random distribution of transformed particles. The mean value of the change in the stress intensity factor created by the random distribution of particles is obtained through statistical analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

McMeeking and Evans (1982) calculated the change of the stress intensity factor induced by the transformation using the weight function theory. Budiansky et al. (1983) used an energy balance relation to obtain the same result. The magnitude of the asymptotic stress intensity change is given by

$$\Delta K = -0.22 \frac{EC_f \theta^T}{(1-\gamma)} \sqrt{H} \quad (1)$$

where H is the width of the transformation zone, θ^T is the dilational component of the transformation strain, C_f is the volume fraction of the transformation particles, and E , γ are the composite modulus and Poisson ratio. Later, Lambropoulos (1986) has taken the shear components of the transformation strain into account. These investigations only took the transformation zone as a homogeneous inclusion with the transformation strain $C_f \varepsilon^T$, or with the different constitutive relation from the matrix, without considering the microstructural detail inside the transformation zone.

In the present paper, the crack tip is assumed to be surrounded by a zone which contains a random distribution of transformed particles. Based on the change of the stress intensity factor introduced by a single particle, the mean value of the change in stress intensity factor created by the random distribution of particles is obtained through statistical analysis. It is found that the change in the stress intensity factor is given by

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** Presently at : 870 Monterey Pass Road, Monterey Park, CA91754, USA

$$\Delta K = \frac{EC_f \theta^T \sqrt{a}}{3\sqrt{2\pi} (1-\gamma)} f(H/a) \quad (2)$$

where, a , H , $f(H/a)$, θ^T , E and ν are the particle radius, width of the transformation zone, a increasing function of H/a , the dilational transformation strain, composite modulus and Poisson ratio, respectively. It is also shown that equation (2) coincides with equation(1) when the particle radius a is negligible small compared with the size H of the transformation zone.

2. FORMULATION OF THE NEW CALCULATION METHOD

Consider a half-plane crack in an infinite elastic solid(Fig. 1). The crack tip is surrounded by a random distribution of transformed particles with transformation strain ϵ^T . According to the weight function theory(Gao, 1989), the change of the stress intensity factor due to a transformed particle is given by

$$\Delta k(z') = \int_{v_p} h_i(x, y, z-z') C_{ijkl} \epsilon_k^T dx dy dz, \quad (3)$$

where $h_i(x, y, z-z')$ is the 3-D weight function, C_{ijkl} is the elastic modulus tensor, and v_p is the region occupied by a transformed partiele. If only the pure dilational transformation strain is taken into account, i. e.

$$\epsilon_{kl}^T = \frac{1}{3} \theta^T \delta_{kl} \quad (4)$$

the mode 1 stress intensity factor can be obtained through equation(3) as

$$\Delta k_I(z') = \frac{4\mu(1-\gamma)}{3} \int_{v_p} P_{,y}(x, y, z-z') \theta^T dx dy dz, \quad (5)$$

where μ is the shear modulus, and

$$P_{,y} = \frac{\cos(\Phi/2) |1 - 8(\frac{\rho^2}{R^2}) \sin^2(\Phi/2)|}{2(1-\gamma)(2\pi)^{3/2} R^2 \rho^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

where

$R^2 = x^2 + y^2 + (z-z')^2$, and ρ , Φ are the polar coordinates in the x, y plane with origin located at the crack tip. The change of the stress intensity factor due to a transformed zone which contains N transformed particles is determined by

$$\Delta K_I = \sum_{i=1}^N \Delta k_I^i = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{4\mu(1+\gamma)}{3} \int_{v_{pi}} P_{,y}(x, y, z-z') \theta^T dx dy dz, \quad (7)$$

where v_{pi} is the region occupied by the i -th particle.

Since the number N and the particle position r_i are random variables, only the average value of ΔK_I is obtained in this paper. When N becomes large, the fluctuation of N can be neglected. Taking the average of equation (8), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Delta K_I \rangle &= \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{4\mu(1+\gamma)}{3} \int_{v_{pi}} P_{,y}(x, y, z-z') \theta^T dx dy dz \right\rangle \\ &= \frac{4\mu(1+\gamma)}{3} \langle N \rangle \left\langle \int_{v_{pi}} P_{,y}(x, y, z-z') \theta^T dx dy dz \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Many particles distribute randomly around the crack tip, and their positions can be treated as trial results of a single particle. This means the frequency distribution of a particle position is known according to a representative specimen. Since the probability density function of a particle position r equals to the frequency distribution approximately, it is determined by (Wang, 1990)

$$f(\vec{r}) = \frac{\lambda(\vec{r})}{\langle N \rangle} \tag{9}$$

where $\lambda(\vec{r})$ the number density function which is defined by

$$\lambda(\vec{r}) = \lim_{\Delta v \rightarrow 0} \frac{N(\vec{r}, \Delta v)}{\Delta v} \tag{10}$$

where $N(\vec{r}, \Delta v)$ is the number of particles within the volume Δv at \vec{r} .

By using equation (9), equation (8) becomes

$$\langle \Delta K_I \rangle = \frac{4\mu(1+\gamma)}{3} \int_V \lambda(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \int_{v(\vec{r})} P_{,j}(x, y, z-z') \theta^\tau dx dy dz, \tag{11}$$

where $v(\vec{r})$ is the region occupied by a particle with its center at \vec{r} , and V is the transformation zone. If the transformed particles are assumed to be spherical particles, each with radius a , the volume integral on a sphere can be approximately obtained an (Wang, 1977). The average of ΔK_I is as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Delta K_I \rangle = & \frac{\mu(1+\gamma)}{3\sqrt{2\pi}(1-\gamma)} C_f \theta^\tau \int_S \frac{3}{5} \rho_0^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_0\right) + \frac{1}{10} |\rho_1|^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_1\right) \\ & + \rho_2^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_2\right) + \rho_3^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_3\right) + \rho_4^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_4\right) |\rho_0 d\rho_0 d\Phi_0, \tag{12} \end{aligned}$$

where, $\rho_i (i=1,2,3,4)$ and $\Phi_i (i=1,2,3,4)$ are functions of ρ_0, Φ_0 and a .

S is the cross section of the transformed zone. To compare with the results given by McMeeking and Evans (1982) the transformed particles are assumed to be cylindrical. Equation (11) becomes

$$\langle \Delta K_I \rangle = \frac{\mu(1+\gamma)}{3\sqrt{2\pi}(1-\gamma)} \theta^\tau \int_S \lambda(x_0, y_0) dx_0 dy_0 \int_{A(r_0)} \rho^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi\right) dx dy, \tag{13}$$

where, $A(r_0)$ is the circular cross section of transformed cylindrical particle with its center at r_0 . If the radius a of the circular cross section is negligible small, and the particle are uniformly distributed, equation (13) becomes

$$\langle \Delta K_I \rangle = \frac{\mu(1+\gamma)}{3(1-\gamma)\sqrt{2\pi}} C_f \theta^\tau \int_S \rho_0^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_0\right) \rho_0 d\rho_0 d\Phi_0 \tag{14}$$

which is in agreement with the results give by McMeeking and Evans (1982) and Budiansky et al. (1983) if the transformed zone S is determined by the critical mean stress.

For plane strain problem, the inner integral in equation (13) can be calculated approximately in the similar manner as in the three-dimensional case (Wang, 1977).

Equation (13) yields

fig. 1. Schematic of transformed particles around a crack

fig. 2. The function f of initial transformation zone.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Delta K_I^p \rangle = & \frac{\mu(1+\gamma)}{3\sqrt{2\pi}(1-\gamma)} C_f \theta^T \int_s \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \rho_0^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_0\right) + \frac{1}{8} |\rho_A^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_A\right) \right. \\ & \left. + \rho_B^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_B\right) + \rho_C^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_C\right) + \rho_D^{-3/2} \cos\left(\frac{3}{2} \Phi_D\right) \right\} \rho_0 d\Phi_0 d\rho_0 \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

Comparing equation (15) with equation (12), one can find that for half-plane crack the toughening effect of the transformed cylindrical particles is different from that induced by the spherical particles.

3. THE CALCULATION FORMULA OF TRANSFORMATION TOUGHENING

For comparing with the results given by McMeeking and Evans (1982) and Budiansky et al. (1983), the transformation-zone contour is determined by the critical mean stress, such that the zone coordinate (ρ, Φ) ahead of the crack tip is given by

$$\rho = \frac{8H}{3\sqrt{3}} \cos^2(\Phi/2), \quad (16)$$

where H is the width of the transformation zone.

3.1 The toughening effect of initial transformation zone

In such case, the transformation region is determined by equation (16). When the transformed spherical particles surround a half-plane crack tip, the change of the stress intensity factor is given by equation (12) as

$$\langle \Delta K_I \rangle = \frac{EC_f \theta^T \sqrt{a}}{3\sqrt{2\pi}(1-\gamma)} f_i \left(\frac{H}{a} \right) \quad (17)$$

where, $f_i(H/a)$ is shown in Fig. 2

For plane strain problem, the transformed particles are assumed to be cylindrical. In such case, the change of the stress intensity factor is given by equation (15) as

$$\langle \Delta K_I^p \rangle = \frac{EC_f \theta^T \sqrt{a}}{3\sqrt{2\pi}(1-\gamma)} f_i^p \left(\frac{H}{a} \right), \quad (18)$$

where, $f_i^p(H/a)$ is shown in Fig. 2.

3.2 The toughening effect of extended transformation zone

When the crack advances into the initial transformation zone, the zone will extend over the crack surfaces if the reverse transformation does not occur. In such case, the integral region in equation (12) and equation (15) can be divided into three parts (Fig. 3), i.e.

$$S_I: 0 \leq \Phi_0 < \frac{\pi}{3}, \quad 0 \leq \rho_0 \leq \frac{8H}{3\sqrt{3}} \cos^2(\Phi_0/2),$$

$$S_{II}: \frac{\pi}{3} \leq \Phi_0 < \pi - \text{tg}^{-1} \frac{H}{L}, \quad 0 \leq \rho_0 \leq H/\sin\Phi_0, \quad (19)$$

$$S_{III}: \pi - \text{tg}^{-1} \frac{H}{L} \leq \Phi_0 < \pi, \quad 0 \leq \rho_0 \leq -\frac{1}{\cos\Phi_0} \quad (20)$$

fig. 3. Schematic of a crack that has advanced into a prior transformation zone by L

fig. 4. The function f of extended transformation zone.

If the transformed particles are assumed to be cylindrical, the asymptotic result of $\langle \Delta K_I \rangle$ is given by equation (15) as

$$\langle \Delta K_I \rangle = -\frac{EC_f \theta^T \sqrt{a}}{3\sqrt{2\pi} (1-\gamma)} f_2(H/a), \quad (20)$$

where the function $f_2(H/a)$ is determined by the integrals on the region given by equation (19). The function $f_2(H/a)$ versus H/a is shown in Fig. 4.

Through the calculation, it is also found that the toughness of material will increase with crack advance L, to produce a resistance curve such as that shown in Fig. 5.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present investigation attempts to develop a new calculation method of transformation toughening by incorporating the microstructural details of material. Under the assumption the a half-plane crack is surrounded by a random distribution of transformed spherical particles, the calculation formula of the change in stress intensity is obtained as

$$\langle \Delta K_I \rangle = \frac{EC_f \theta^T \sqrt{a}}{3\sqrt{2\pi} (1-\gamma)} f(H/a) \quad (21)$$

fig. 5. R curve predicted from stress intensity factor analysis.

It is also found that when the radius of particle is negligible small, equation (21) coincides with that obtained by McMeeking and Evans (1982).

We used the same transformation zone as that used by McMeeking and Evans (1982) without considering the effect of the residual stress field (See Amazigo and Budiansky, 1988), which needs further investigation.

REFERENCES

1. Amazigo, J. C. and Budiansky, B. (1988). Steady-state crack growth in supercritically transforming materials. *Int. J. Solids Structures*, 24,751-755.
2. Budiansky, B., Hutchinson, J. W. and Lambropoulos, J. C. (1983). Continuum theory of dilatant transformation toughening in ceramics. *Int. J. Solids Structures*, 19,335-355.
3. Gao, H. (1988). Application of 3-D weight functions - I formulations of crack interactions with transformation strains and dislocations. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, 37,133-153.
4. Lambropoulos, J. C. (1986). Shear, shape and orientation effects in transformation toughening. *Int J. Solids Structures*, 22,1083-1106.
5. McMeeking, R. M. and Evans, A. G. (1982). Mechanics of transformation toughening in brittle materials. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 63,241-248.
6. Wang, B. (1990), A General theory on media with randomly distributed inclusions, part I: the average field behaviors. *ASME J. Appl. Mech.* (to be published).
7. Wang, L. X, et al, (1977), Handbook of mathematics, Higher Education press, Beijing, 309-315, (in Chinese).